

WEAR PROPERTIES OF HYBRID METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of this study is to investigate the wear properties of Saffil/Al, Saffil/Al₂O₃/Al and Saffil/SiC/Al hybrid metal matrix composites fabricated by squeeze casting method. Wear tests were done on a pin-on-disk friction & wear tester under both dry and lubrication conditions. The wear properties of the three composites were evaluated in many respects. The effects of Saffil, Al₂O₃ particles and SiC particles on the wear behavior of the composites were elucidated. Wear mechanisms were analyzed by observing the worn surfaces of the composites. The variation of coefficient of friction (COF) during the wear process was recorded by using a computer. Under dry sliding condition, Saffil/SiC/Al showed the best wear resistance under high temperature and high load. Compared with the dry sliding condition, all three composites showed excellent wear resistance when lubricated by liquid paraffin. Under lubrication condition, Saffil/Al showed the best wear resistance among them, and its COF value is the smallest. The dominant wear mechanism of the composites under lubricated condition was microploughing, but microcracking also occurred to them to different extents.

KEYWORDS: Hybrid Metal Matrix Composites, Squeeze Casting Method, Wear Properties, Wear Mechanism, Lubrication

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, aluminum Metal Matrix Composites (MMCs) used for tribological components have attracted more and more interests. They are widely used as high speed rotating or reciprocating mass items such as pistons, connecting rods, drive shafts, brake rotors and cylinder bores [1]. Compared with the corresponding monolithic alloys, aluminum matrix composites are attractive because of their improved strength, stiffness, creep behavior, wear resistance and low thermal expansion [2]. Their applications will be greatly expanded in the near future if problems like cost and fabricating are well resolved.

Many researches have been carried out on the wear behaviors of aluminum MMCs recently [3-14]. A transition from mild wear to severe wear of hybrid MMCs can be induced by changes in load or temperature [15]. Any tribological components are supposed to work in the mild wear region and try to avoid the severe wear region, so it is of interest to know the transition load or temperature of the hybrid MMCs. The change of wear mechanism does not always mean an increase in weight loss, but it may result in the increasing of friction force or changing of microstructure or others.

Lubricant is widely used in industry field as it contributes to decreasing of friction, transporting of heat and worn debris from system, and bearing of part of the applied loading

to the system [16]. The liquid paraffin is a good lubricant for aluminum MMCs. Yoshiro Iwai *et al.* found that in paraffin oil, the wear rates of 7004-T6 and 2024-T4 were about 1/10 the wear rates under dry conditions [17]. Pan *et al.* found that the main wear mechanism of 2124Al-SiCw composite was abrasive wear through plowing and polishing for lubricated sliding [18]. In industry field, the tribological components are inevitably to work under high temperature due to the heat generated or other factors. So the wear behavior under high temperature becomes important sometimes. The dry sliding wear behaviors of aluminum MMCs are available in literature, but the wear properties under lubricated conditions, as well as high temperature, are very limited.

Saffil fibers, Al₂O₃ particles and SiC particles are usually used as reinforcements of aluminum alloys. But how do these reinforcements effecting on the wear behavior of aluminum MMCs? The answer to this question would be very helpful in getting a general idea of the wear properties of hybrid MMCs and designing of hybrid MMCs for tribological use. In this research, three kinds of hybrid MMCs, named Saffil/Al, Saffil/Al₂O₃/Al and Saffil/SiC/Al, were developed, and the wear properties of them under both dry and lubricated conditions were evaluated.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

Materials

The three composites all contained 20vol.% reinforcements. Saffil/Al₂O₃/Al contained 5vol.% Saffil fibers and 15vol.% Al₂O₃ particles. Saffil/SiC/Al contained 5vol.% Saffil fibers and 15vol.% SiC particles. The small fraction of Saffil fibers in Saffil/Al₂O₃/Al and Saffil/SiC/Al was used to reinforce the aluminum matrix and make the composites easier to fabricate, but the wear properties of these two kinds of composites were determined by the particles.

The matrix alloy was AC8A. The Saffil fibers (δ -alumina fibers) were fabricated by ICI (U.K.), having an average length of 150 μ m and average density of 3.3g/cm³. The size of the Al₂O₃ particle was 40 μ m. The SiC particles, which were fabricated by Imperial Polychemical Corp. (U.S.A.), had an average length of 30 μ m and average density of 3.2g/cm³. Fig. 1 shows the SEM graphs of Saffil fibers, Al₂O₃ particles and SiC particles. The composites were all fabricated by squeeze casting method. After squeeze casting, cast ingots were treated by T6 heat treatment. The reinforcements were homogeneously distributed, as shown in Fig. 2.

Experimental Details

The wear behavior of Saffil/Al, Saffil/Al₂O₃/Al and Saffil/SiC/Al hybrid MMCs was investigated on a pin-on-disk friction & wear tester. Fig. 3 shows the schematic diagram of the friction & wear tester under lubricated condition.

The specimens were 30mm in diameter and 8mm in thickness. The counter material was SCM 440. The diameter of the steel pins was 5mm, and the diameter of the pin's top surface was 4.3mm after chamfered. The contact surfaces of the specimens and pins were all smoothed by

Fig. 1. SEM graphs of the reinforcements: (a) Saffil fibers, (b) Al₂O₃ particles and (c) SiC particles. 500×.

Fig. 2. Optical micrographs of the specimens' surfaces show that the reinforcements are homogeneously distributed. (a) Saffil/Al, (b) Saffil/Al₂O₃/Al and (c) Saffil/SiC/Al. 50×.

1500 grit SiC paper. The rotating diameter of the pin on the specimen's surface was 23mm. The sliding speed was 0.36m/s. The weight losses were measured by using an electronic balance with a sensitivity of 0.1mg. The applied load under lubricated condition was 240N. In order to remove the oleaginous organic substances from the specimens' surface, the specimens were cleaned in an acetone bath and dried in hot air before and after the tests. The pins were also cleaned with acetone before the tests. The long sliding distance wear tests under lubricated condition were done by an incremental method [16]. The total distance was 8000m and an increment was 2000m. After each increment, the specimen was removed, cleaned by acetone and dried in hot air, then weighted and remounted in the wear tester at the same location, and then the test was continued using fresh lubricant.

The wear process was controlled by a computer. Friction force, coefficient of friction (COF), wear depth and temperature were recorded as a function of time.

Fig. 3. A schematic diagram of the friction & wear tester under lubricated condition.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Results under Dry Sliding Condition

According to the well-known Archard's equation [19], the wear rate was related to the hardness of the material. Generally, hybrid MMCs were composed of two or more kinds of materials with different hardness. Moreover, the hardness of the contacting surface might be different from the bulk hardness due to strain hardening, material transfer or other factors. So the determination of wear properties of the composites became more complicated.

Fig. 4 (a) shows the weight losses under various temperatures and load of 1kg. It was obvious that Saffil/SiC/Al showed the best wear resistance under high temperature. It had the highest transition temperature, which was about 200°C. There was little difference between the wear resistance of Saffil/Al and Saffil/Al₂O₃/Al under various temperatures, and the transition temperature of them was both about 150°C. The SiC particles contributed to the good wear resistance of Saffil/SiC/Al. The wear resistance of SiC particles was better than that of Saffil fibers and Al₂O₃ particles under high temperature. The hardness of SiC was very high even under high temperature. Under high temperature, the matrix became ductile, so the applied load was conducted to the reinforcements. The wear resistance of the reinforcements under high temperature determined the wear resistance of the composites. Saffil fiber was made from δ -type Al₂O₃, and it had the similar hardness, which played an important role in the wear resistance of the material according to Archard, with the Al₂O₃ particle. So the wear resistance of Saffil/Al and Saffil/Al₂O₃/Al was very similar.

It was also shown in Fig. 4 (a) that Saffil/SiC/Al had the biggest weight loss under room temperature. This was because the dominant wear mechanism under room temperature was two- or three-body abrasive wear, and the hardest SiC particles resulted in the biggest weight loss of Saffil/SiC/Al. The dominant wear mechanism changed to adhesion and molten wear as temperature increased. When molten wear occurred, the wear was very serious.

Fig. 4 (b) shows the weight losses under room temperature and various loads. Saffil/SiC/Al showed the best wear resistance under various loads, while the wear resistances of Saffil/Al and Saffil/Al₂O₃/Al were almost the same.

Results under Lubricated Condition

Fig. 5 shows the result of weight losses under various sliding distances and temperatures. The weight losses of Saffil/SiC/Al and Saffil/Al₂O₃/Al increased abruptly at the early stage of

Fig. 4. Dry sliding wear behavior under: (a) various temperatures and load of 1kg and (b) room temperature and various loads.

sliding distance, as shown in Fig. 5 (a), and increased slightly, or even ceased to increase, after sliding distance of 2000m. As for Saffil/Al, the weight loss increased slightly from the

beginning of the test. Saffil/Al showed the best wear resistance, while Saffil/SiC/Al showed the worst wear resistance under room temperature.

As shown in Fig. 5 (b), Saffil/Al still exhibited the best wear resistance under temperature of 100°C. But the wear resistance of Saffil/SiC/Al and Saffil/Al₂O₃/Al was different from room temperature, the wear resistance of Saffil/SiC/Al was better than that of Saffil/Al₂O₃/Al under temperature of 100°C.

At room temperature, the wear resistance of Saffil/Al₂O₃/Al was better than that of Saffil/SiC/Al. This was because SiC particle was harder than alumina particle. The hard particle was destructive to the wear resistance of the composite. But at high temperature, it was different. The wear resistance of Saffil/Al₂O₃/Al was worse than Saffil/SiC/Al. This was because at high temperature, the matrix became ductile, so the applied load was conducted to the particles. The wear resistance of SiC particles was better than that of Al₂O₃ particles, so at this temperature, the weight loss of Saffil/Al₂O₃/Al was bigger than that of Saffil/SiC/Al.

Fig. 6 shows the two kinds of wear modes. Saffil/Al exhibited the best wear resistance because there were no hard particles acting as abrasives, while there were some hard particles acting as abrasives for Saffil/SiC/Al and Saffil/Al₂O₃/Al, so the weight loss of Saffil/SiC/Al and Saffil/Al₂O₃/Al was bigger than that of Saffil/Al. As shown in Fig. 5 (a), the weight loss of Saffil/SiC/Al and Saffil/Al₂O₃/Al increased only slightly after sliding distance of 2000m. This was because most of the particles on the surface were pulled out at the early stage, and after sliding distance of 2000m, there were few particles acting as abrasives.

Fig. 5. Comparison of the lubricated wear behavior of the three materials under various temperatures: (a) Room Temperature, (b) 100°C.

Fig. 6. The three materials have different wear modes under lubricated condition. (a) Wear mode of Saffil/Al; (b) Wear mode of Saffil/Al₂O₃/Al and Saffil/SiC/Al.

Fig. 7. Result of wear depth vs. sliding distance under various temperatures: (a) room temperature and (b) 100°C.

The wear depths of them increased abruptly at the early stage and kept increasing with sliding distance, as shown in Fig. 7. It was obvious that Saffil/SiC/Al had the deepest wear depth under lubricated condition. Actually, the total wear depth included the wear of the pin and the wear of the specimen. The wear of the pin was very serious.

It was not difficult to find that the weight loss almost ceased to increase after sliding distance of 2000m, while the wear depth kept increasing all the time. This seemingly contradiction result might be explained like this. As the particles were pulled out and became debris, pits occurred, but at the same time, some debris trapped into the pits and might form a transfer layer. So the transfer layer prevented the wear of the specimen and the weight loss ceased to increase. It could be concluded that it was the wear of the steel pin, instead of the specimen, that caused the increasing of the wear depth. The wear depth of Saffil/SiC/Al was the deepest, which was because that the SiC particle was the hardest and the damage to the steel pin was the most serious. The total wear depth under 100°C was deeper than that of room temperature, this was because the materials became ductile under high temperature, and the materials were easily to be removed from the surface. Moreover, there was a decreasing of viscosity of the lubricant as temperature increased, and the load carried by the lubricant film decreased according to Reynolds' equation [20]. The lubricant film might have broken down under this temperature.

Worn Surfaces Analysis

The worn surfaces were observed though SEM. Fig. 8 shows the morphologies of the worn surfaces of the composites under dry sliding. It was found from Fig. 8 (b)(c) that the worn surfaces of Saffil/Al₂O₃/Al and Saffil/SiC/Al were filled with grooves paralleling to the sliding direction, while the grooves on the worn surface of Saffil/Al were not so obvious. This was because that the wear mechanism under room temperature was abrasive wear. For Saffil/Al₂O₃/Al and Saffil/SiC/Al, some hard particles were pulled out and acted as three-body abrasives, which resulted in the serious grooves.

Fig. 8 (d)(e)(f) shows the SEM graphs of the worn surfaces at 150°C. The worn surfaces of Saffil/Al and Saffil/Al₂O₃/Al were very smooth, which was because of the shear deformation. Under this temperature, the matrix became ductile, so the wear behavior of the reinforcements played an important role on the wear behavior of the composites. The reinforcements could be found on the worn surfaces of Saffil/Al₂O₃/Al and Saffil/SiC/Al, as shown by ellipses in Fig. 8 (e)(f). Under this temperature, the dominant wear mechanism was adhesive wear.

Fig. 8. SEM graphs of the worn surfaces under dry sliding: (a)(d) Saffil/Al, (b)(e) Saffil/Al₂O₃/Al and (c)(f) Saffil/SiC/Al. (a)(b)(c) for room temperature and load of 10kg, and (d)(e)(f) for 150°C and load of 1kg.

Fig. 9 shows the morphologies of the worn surfaces of the composites under lubricated condition and sliding distance of 8000m. It was found that the worn surfaces of Saffil/Al₂O₃/Al and Saffil/SiC/Al were filled with grooves paralleling to the sliding direction, while the grooves on the worn surface of Saffil/Al were not so obvious. The grooves occurred here could be thought as a characteristic of microploughing [21]. The grooves in Fig. 9 (b)(c)(e)(f) were discontinuous and cracks were found on the worn surfaces. The occurrence of cracks was due to the pulling-out of some particles, i.e., microcracking. Microcracking of Saffil/SiC/Al was serious than Saffil/Al₂O₃/Al.

Fig. 9. SEM graphs of the worn surfaces under lubricated condition, load of 24kg and sliding distance of 8000m: (a)(d) Saffil/Al, (b)(e) Saffil/Al₂O₃/Al and (c)(f) Saffil/SiC/Al. (a)(b)(c) for room temperature and (d)(e)(f) for 100°C.

Fig. 10. SEM graphs of the pins' surfaces against: (a) Saffil/Al, (b) Saffil/Al₂O₃/Al and (c) Saffil/SiC/Al, room temperature.

As for Saffil/Al, microcracking was not obvious, and grooves were almost not found on the worn surfaces. This was because that there were no hard particles acted as abrasives, but the grooves could be found on the surface of the pin, as shown in Fig. 10 (a). Saffil fibers could be found on the worn surface, but they were not pulled out, which suggested a good bonding between the fibers and the matrix, as show in Fig. 9 (a) by an ellipse. The worn surfaces were all very smooth and flat, which was due to the polishing of the surfaces.

It was also found that wear of the pin against Saffil/SiC/Al was serious than that of the pins against Saffil/Al and Saffil/Al₂O₃/Al. The grooves in Fig. 10 (c) were deeper and wider than Fig. 10 (a) and (b). It was the high strength of Saffil/SiC/Al and the hard SiC particles that caused the serious wear of the pin. There was little difference between the worn surfaces of the pins under room temperature and 100°C, which suggested that the dominant wear mechanism remained unchanged at 100°C.

COF Characteristics

The COF value was generally determined by the following equation [21]:

$$\mu = \frac{\tau_c \cdot A}{F_N} \quad (1)$$

Where τ_c was the critical shear strength of the material, A was the contacting area and F_N was the normal load. COF increased with increasing critical shear strength. Critical shear strength decreased with increasing temperature, so the COF value of room temperature should be bigger than that of high temperature.

The COF characteristics under dry sliding, load of 1kg and various temperatures were shown in Fig. 11. The fluctuation of COF values became serious after 150°C, which was due to the occurrence of adhesion. It was obvious Saffil/SiC/Al had the maximum COF value and its COF variation was the most serious. The COF value was around 0.4, which was about three times that of lubricated condition.

Fig. 11. COF characteristics of the three materials under dry sliding at load of 1kg and various temperatures: (a) Saffil/Al, (b) Saffil/Al₂O₃/Al and (c) Saffil/SiC/Al.

Fig. 12. COF characteristics of the three materials under lubricated condition at load of 24kg: (a)(d) Saffil/Al, (b)(e) Saffil/Al₂O₃/Al and (c)(f) Saffil/SiC/Al. (a)(b)(c) for room temperature and (d)(e)(f) for 100°C.

Fig. 12 shows the COF characteristics under lubricated condition. The COF values fluctuated greatly at the early stage, and tended to reach some constant value as sliding distance increased. Under room temperature, this constant value was 0.15, 0.16 and 0.17 for Saffil/Al, Saffil/Al₂O₃/Al and Saffil/SiC/Al, respectively. And under 100°C, this constant value was 0.12, 0.14 and 0.15 for Saffil/Al, Saffil/Al₂O₃/Al and Saffil/SiC/Al, respectively. Obviously, Saffil/Al had the minimum COF value due to its smallest critical shear strength. The COF values of 100°C were smaller than those of room temperature, which was because of the decreasing of critical shear strength as temperature increased. The COF values of Saffil/Al and Saffil/Al₂O₃/Al at the early stage were not very big. It was because the materials were relatively soft and the reinforcements could not resist the plastic deformation on the surfaces. The COF value of Saffil/SiC/Al was the biggest. This was due to its greater strength, rendering the composite most difficult to deform.

The COF fluctuations under 100°C were more serious than those under room temperature. This was because the materials became ductile at high temperature, and the misfitting of the remounted specimen would cause serious wear of the specimen. On the other hand, the viscosity of the lubricant decreased as the temperature increased, which resulted in the decreasing of the thickness of the lubrication film, so the load carried by the lubricant decreased, which would also cause the serious direct contacting of the metals and therefore cause the increasing of COF. But the COF would decrease as contacting conditions improved.

CONCLUSIONS

The wear behaviors of Saffil/Al, Saffil/Al₂O₃/Al and Saffil/SiC/Al hybrid MMCs were investigated under both dry and lubricated conditions. The following conclusions were drawn. Under dry sliding condition, Saffil/SiC/Al showed the best wear resistance under high temperature and high load, while the wear resistances of Saffil/Al and Saffil/Al₂O₃/Al were very similar. Under dry sliding condition, the dominant wear mechanism was abrasive wear

under mild load and room temperature, and the dominant wear mechanism changed to adhesive wear as load or temperature increased. Molten wear occurred at high temperature. Saffil/Al shows the best wear resistance under lubricated sliding. Under lubricated condition, the wear resistance of Saffil/Al₂O₃/Al is better than that of Saffil/SiC/Al under room temperature, but under high temperature, Saffil/SiC/Al shows better wear resistance. The dominant wear mechanism of these composites under lubricated sliding is microploughing, but microcracking also occurs to them to different extents. Particles, especially hard particles, are detrimental to the wear resistance of aluminum MMCs under lubricated sliding.

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